

INVENTORY OF NANTUCKET FUNGI

6/04 to the present

Compiled by Dr. Lawrence Millman

Agaricus arvensis (Horse Mushroom). Meadow and grassy areas. Squam Farm
Agaricus porphyrocephala. Grass and sandy soil. Near Quaise.
Agaricus silvaticus (Red-Staining Agaricus). Squam Swamp.
Agrocybe dura. On wood chips. Tuppenny Links. Spring.
Agrocybe praecox (Spring Agrocybe). On woody debris. Squam Swamp. Spring.
Amanita bisporigera. Under pine. Coskata Woods. Infrequent. (9/05)
Amanita brunnescens (Cleft Foot). In wooded areas around Nantucket.
Amanita citrina (Citron Amanita). Oak and pine woods. Common around Nantucket.
Amanita cokeri (Coker's Amanita). In woods. Lost Farm.
Amanita crenulata. Under white pine. State Forest. Infrequent. (9/05)
Amanita fulva (Tawny Grisette). Near tupelo. Squam Swamp.
Amanita inaurata (Strangulated Amanita). Under white pine. State Forest.
Amanita muscaria var. *formosa* (Fly Agaric). With pine, esp. pitch pine. Lost Farm and Coskata Woods.
Amanita rubescens (The Blusher). In mixed woods. Frequent.
Amanita rubescens var. *alba*. In wooded area. Squam Farm. Infrequent. (10/07)
Amanita vaginata (Grisette). State Forest. Frequent.
Antrodia albida. On white pine logs. State Forest and Hidden Forest.
Arcyria denudata (Purple Slime). Well-rotted log. Hidden Forest.
Armillariella mellea (Honey Mushroom). On wood and woody debris. Frequent.
Asterophora lycoperdoides (Powder Cap). On rotting *Russula* species. State Forest.
Auricularia auricula (Wood Ear). On pine log. Squam Swamp.
Bisporella citrina (Lemon Drops). On decorticated wood. Frequent.
Bjerkandera adusta (Smoky Polypore). Oak logs. Squam Swamp.
Boletinellus (= *Gyrodon*) *merulioides* (Ash Tree Bolete). Near ash. Squam Swamp.
Boletus affinis var. *maculosus* (Spotted Bolete). Under beech. State Forest.
Boletus bicolor (Two Colored Bolete). Under oak. State Forest.
Boletus parasiticus. Parasitic on *Scleroderma* species. Lost Farm and Squam Farm.
Bovista pila (Tumbling Puffball). Sandy soil. Lost Farm.
Calocera cornea (Tuning Fork). Decorticated logs. Squam Swamp.
Calvatia cyathiformis (Purple Spored Puffball). In grass near Oldest House. Infrequent. (10/07)
Cantharellus minor (Small Chantarelle). In moss. Squam Swamp.
Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa (Coral Slime). On rotten wood. Frequent.
Cerrena unicolor (Mossy Maze Polypore). On deciduous wood. Frequent.
Cheimonophyllum candidissimus (White Oysterette). On tupelo log. Squam Swamp.
Clavicornia pyxidata (Crown Tipped Coral). On poplar logs. Hidden Forest.
Clavulinopsis fusiformis (Golden Spindles). In moss. Squam Swamp.
Clavulinopsis aurantiocinnabarina. In moss. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/04)
Clitocybe clavipes (Club Foot). Under white pine. State Forest.
Clitocybe nuda (Blewit). Woody debris. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.
Collybia acervata (Clustered Collybia). Wood mulch. Nantucket town.

Collybia dryophila (Oak Loving Collybia). With oak. Frequent.
Collybia maculata (Spotted Collybia). On humus. Lost Farm.
Collybia maculata var. *scorzonerea*. On humus/grass. Lost Farm. Infrequent. (9/05)
Collybia tuberosa. On decayed mushrooms. Quaise.
Coprinus atramentarius (Tippler's Bane). On woody debris. Common around Nantucket.
Coprinus plicatilis (Japanese Umbrella Inky). On mulch in front of Drake House. Infrequent. (5/04)
Coprinus quadrifidus (Scaly Inky Cap). On mulch pile. Tuppenny Links. Infrequent. (5/04)
Cortinarius alboviolaceus (Silvery Violet Cort). Under beech. Squam Swamp.
Cortinarius caninus (Dog Cort). Squam Swamp.
Cortinarius iodes (Viscid Violet Cort). In forested areas. Frequent.
Cortinarius pseudosalor. Near hemlock. Quaise.
Craterellus fallax (Black Trumpet). Near oak and beech. Squam Swamp.
Crepidotus applanatus (Flat Crep). Red maple log. Hidden Forest.
Crepidotus mollis (Jelly Crep). Maple and oak logs. Squam Swamp.
Cribraria argillacea (slime mold). Well-rotted pine log. Squam Swamp.
Crucibulum laeve (White Bird's Nest). On woody debris, esp. in Nantucket town.
Cryptoporus volvatus (Veiled Polypore). On Japanese black pine at Tuppenny Links. Infrequent. (5/04)
Daedalea quercina (Thick Maze Polypore). On oak logs. Tuppenny Links.
Daedaleopsis confragosa (Thin Maze Polypore). On deciduous wood. Frequent.
Daldinia concentrica (Carbon Balls). On dead scrub oak branches. Middle Moors.
Entoloma arborivum (Aborted Entoloma). On woody debris. Squam Swamp.
Entoloma sinuatum (= *lividum*). (Lead Poisoner) Squam Swamp.
Entoloma strictius (Straight Stalked Entoloma). On rotting wood. Squam Swamp.
Exidia glandulosa (Black Witch's Butter). On oak logs. Squam Swamp.
Exobasidium rhododendrii (Azalea Gall). On wild azalea. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (5/04)
Favolus alveolaris (Hexagonal Pored Polypore). On deciduous wood branches. Coskata Woods.
Fuligo septica (Scrambled Egg Slime). On logs and leaf litter. Squam Swamp.
Galerina autumnalis (Deadly Galerina). On rotting log. Squam Swamp.
Galerina paludosa. On moss. Squam Swamp.
Ganoderma lucidum (Ling Chih). On scrub oak logs. Middle Moors.
Ganoderma tsugae (Hemlock Varnish Shelf). On Japanese black pine. Tuppenny Links.
Geastrum saccatum (Rounded Earthstar). In dunes. Surfside Beach.
Gloeophyllum sepiarium (Yellow-Red Gill Polypore). On white pine log. Lost Farm.
Grifola frondosa (Hen of the Woods). On dead oak stump. Hidden Forest.
Gymnopilus penetrans (Little Gym). On dead coniferous wood. State Forest. Frequent.
Hebeloma crustuliniforme (Poison Pie). Under pitch pine in front of Nantucket airport. Infrequent. (10/07)
Hemitrichia serpula (Pretzel Slime). On rotten wood. Hidden Forest.
Hydnochaete olivaceum (Brown Toothed Crust). On dead deciduous branches. Frequent.
Hydnochaete tabacina (Reddish Brown Crust). Beech branches. Squam Swamp.
Hydnum (= *Dentinum*) *repandum* (Sweet Tooth). Near hemlock. Squam Swamp.
Hydnum (= *Dentinum*) *repandum* var. *album*. Near hemlock. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/05)
Hygrocybe borealis (= *niveus*) (White Waxy Cap). In moss. Frequent.
Hygrocybe canescens. Near hemlock. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/05)

Hygrocybe coccinea (Scarlet Waxy Cap). In swamp areas of Squam Swamp.
Hygrocybe flavescens (Golden Waxy Cap). In moss. Squam Swamp and Tuckernuck Island.
Hygrocybe marginata (Orange Gilled Waxy Cap). In wooden areas. Frequent.
Hygrocybe nitidus. On leaf litter. Squam Swamp.
Hygrocybe psitticinus (Parrot Mushroom). In moss and leaf litter. Squam Swamp.
Hygrophoropsis aurantiaca (False Chanterelle). Around white pine. State Forest. Frequent.
Hygrophorus eburneus (White Waxy Cap). Coskata Woods.
Hypholoma fasciculare (Sulphur Tuft). Woody debris. Squam Swamp.
Hypholoma sublateritium (Brick Tops). On rotting wood. Frequent.
Hypholoma udum. In wet moss. Squam Swamp.
Hypocrea gelatinosa (Yellow Cushion). On rotting wood. Squam Swamp.
Hypomyces chrysospermus (Golden Hypomyces). On Bolete species. Quaise. Infrequent. (10/07)
Hypoxyton annulatum. On black oak stumps. Tuckernuck Island.
Hypoxyton fragiforme. On dead beech logs. Frequent.
Inonotus (= *Onnia*) *tomentosus* (Woolly Velvet Polypore). Under pitch pine. Lost Farm.
Irpex lacteus (Milk White Toothed Polypore). On dead deciduous wood. Frequent.
Laccaria laccata (Common Laccaria). In poor or sandy soil. Frequent.
Laccaria trullisata (Sand Loving Laccaria). Sandy soil. Coskata.
Lactarius lignyotus (Chocolate Milky). Under white pine. State Forest.
Lactarius vinaceorufescens (Yellow Latex Milky). Under pine. Frequent.
Laetiporus sulphureus (Chicken of the Woods). Oak log. Squam Swamp.
Laxitextum roseo-carneum. On decaying hardwood branches. Quaise.
Leccinum insigne (Aspen Scaber Stalk). Under poplar. Lost Farm.
Leocarpis fragilis (Insect Egg Slime). On rotten wood. Squam Swamp.
Lepiota cristata (Malodorous Lepiota). Mulch pile. Lost Farm. Infrequent. (9/05)
Lycogala epidendrum (Wolf's Milk Slime). On dead wood. Common around Nantucket.
Lycoperdon marginatum (local name: Sheep's Knuckles). Sand or sandy soil. Frequent.
Lycoperdon pyriforme (Pear Shaped Puffball). On stumps and debris in forested areas.
Marasmius oreades (Fairy Ring Mushroom). In grass. Mormon Cemetery.
Maramius scorodiscus (Garlic Marasmius). In grass. Old Quaker Cemetery.
Mollisia cinerea (Grey Cup). Under dead logs in wet areas.
Mutinus caninus (Dog Stinkhorn). Dunes. Infrequent. (9/07)
Mycena galericulata (Common Mycena). On deciduous and coniferous wood. Squam Swamp.
Mycena haematopus (Bleeding Mycena). On maple logs. Squam Swamp and Hidden Forest.
Nolanea quadrata (Salmon Unicorn Entoloma). In moss. Squam Swamp.
Nolanea murrarii (Yellow Unicorn Entoloma). On ground. Squam Swamp.
Nolanea lutea. On ground. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/06)
Oligoporus fragilis (Brown Staining Polypore). On white pine logs. State Forest.
Oxyporus populinus (Mossy Maple Polypore). On maple. State Forest and Coskata Woods.
Panaeolus campanulatus (Bell-Cap Panaeolus). On horse dung. State Forest. Infrequent. (10/07)
Panellus stipticus (Luminescent Panellus). On dead wood. Frequent.
Phaeolus schweinitzii (Dyer's Polypore). At base of pine trees. Squam Swamp.
Peziza varia. On mulch pile. Tuppenny Links. Infrequent. (5/06)
Phaeocalicium polyporaeum. On caps of *Trichaptum biformis*. Frequent.
Phanerochaete chrysorhiza (Spreading Yellow Tooth). Underside of deciduous logs. Squam Swamp.

Pholiota aurivella (Golden Pholiota). On dead maple. Squam Swamp.

Pluteus cervinus (Fawn Mushroom). On maple logs. Squam Swamp.

Polyporus squamosus (Dryad's Saddle). On buried wood near Jared Coffin House and in Coskata.

Psathyrella delineata. On tupelo stump. Squam Swamp.

Psathyrella foenisecii (Lawn Mower's Mushroom). In grassy areas around Nantucket. Spring.

Psathyrella hydrophila (Clustered Psathyrella). On maple logs and stumps. Hidden Forest.

Psilocybe atrobrunnea. In sphagnum. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/05)

Ramaria stricta (Straight Branches Coral). Under pine. Squam Swamp.

Ramariopsis kunzei (White Coral). On ground. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/06)

Rhytisma acerinum (Tar Spot of Maple). On maple leaves. Frequent.

Russula crustosa (Green Quilt Russula). Under oak. Squam Swamp.

Russula dissimulans (Blackening Russula). Near white pine. State Forest.

Russula emetica (Emetic Russula). In forested areas around Nantucket.

Russula laurocerasi (Almond Scented Russula). Under or near maple. Lost Farm.

Russula violacea (= *krombholzii*). (Blackish Red Russula). In woods. Quaise.

Schizophyllum commune (Split Gill). On branches and dead logs. Hidden Forest and Tuppenny Links.

Scleroderma areolatum. In parking area. Squam Swamp.

Scleroderma bovista. Sandy soil. Tuckernuck Island.

Scleroderma cepa (Hardball). Woodchips in front of Hyline office, Nantucket town. Infrequent. (10/07)

Scleroderma citrinum (Pigskin Poison Puffball). In sandy soil around Nantucket. Frequent.

Scleroderma polyrhizon (= *geaster*). Sand and gravel. Tuckernuck Island.

Scutellinia scutellata (Eyelash Cup). On rotting logs. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.

Stemonitis splendens (Chocolate Tube Slime). Red maple log. Hidden Forest.

Stereum complicatum (Crowded Parchment). On dead wood. Frequent.

Stereum ostrea (False Turkey Tail). On dead wood. Frequent.

Stereum rugosum. On dead swamp maple tree. Hidden Forest. Infrequent. (9/06)

Stropharia rugosoannulata (Wine Cap). In wood chips and gardens around Nantucket town.

Suillus granulatus (Granulated Suillus). Under white pine. Common in forested areas.

Suillus luteus (Slippery Jack). Under white pine and pitch pine in State Forest.

Thelephora terrestris (Earth Vase). In sandy soil. Tuckernuck Island.

Trametes hirsuta (Hairy Turkey Tail). On dead deciduous wood or in wounds. State Forest.

Trametes ochracea (Yellow Turkey Tail). On maple log. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (10/07)

Trametes pubescens. On tupelo logs. Squam Swamp.

Trametes versicolor (Turkey Tail). On dead deciduous wood. Frequent.

Tremella mesenterica (Witch's Butter). On dead wood. Hidden Forest.

Tremella reticulata. On wood. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/06)

Tremellodendron pallidum (= *schweinitzii*). Near tupelo. Squam Swamp.

Trichaptum abietinum. On coniferous logs. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.

Trichaptum bififormis (Purple Toothed Polypore). On dead deciduous stumps and logs. Frequent.

Trichoglossum farlowii. In wet moss. Squam Swamp.

Trichoglossum hirsutum (Hairy Earth Tongue). In wet moss. Squam Swamp.

Tricholoma resplendens (= *columbetta*). (White Trich) Under pine. Hidden Forest.

Tricholoma sejunctum. Under pine. Hidden Forest.

Tylopilus alboater. Under oak. Coskata Woods. Infrequent. (9/05)

Tylopilus felleus (Bitter Bolete). In wooded areas around Nantucket.

Tyromyces chioneus (White Cheese Polypore). Dead deciduous wood. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.

Ustulina deusta (Carbon Cushion). On living maple. Squam Swamp.

Ustulina deusta (asexual stage). On dead tupelo log. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (10/07)

Infrequent=found only once on Nantucket